

SENSITIVITY OF FIRE STRUCTURAL PERFORMANCE OF CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED EPOXY LAMINATES TO PLY ORIENTATION

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experimental investigation into the structural response and failure of aerospace carbon-fibre epoxy laminates during exposure to fire. A comparative study into the fire structural resistance of four laminates with different stacking sequences of the 0°, 90°, +45° and -45° plies is presented. Fire structural tests are performed on the laminates subjected to one-sided heating representative of the heat radiated by fire and constant tension loading. Testing revealed that the internal temperatures of the laminates is dependent on their ply orientation; with laminates with a 0° ply at the heated surface reaching higher back face temperatures than laminates with a 45° surface ply. Laminates with a 45° surface ply experience more extensive heat-induced delamination cracking which lowers the effective through-thickness thermal conductivity. It is also found that the softening rate and stress rupture time depends on the ply orientation, most notably at low applied tensile stresses. Laminates with a 0° surface ply weaken at a faster rate and fail earlier in fire than laminates with a 45° surface ply. The research indicates that the fire structural survivability of carbon-epoxy aircraft structures may be strongly dependent on the ply stacking sequence, with 45° plies at the surface providing the best performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

For civil passenger aircraft, a significant number of fatalities and injuries in otherwise survivable accidents are associated with the effects of fire [1]. In an accident at Manchester airport in 1985, an external fire during take-off entered the cabin by burning through the B737 aluminium fuselage [2]. The loss of life was attributed to rapid fuselage burn-through into the passenger cabin. This incident highlights the importance of aircraft materials having burn-through fire resistance. In 1996, an in-flight fire ignited in a passenger aircraft, causing the death of all 110 passengers and crew after failure of the flight control systems due to the extreme heat and subsequent structural collapse [3].

Figure 1: Fire damage on the composite fuselage of B787 [4].

Shortly after, in 1998, a MD-11 aircraft made a crash landing due to in-flight fire causing the death of 229 passengers [5]. More recently the carbon-fibre epoxy fuselage of a Boeing 787 sustained heat and fire damage due to faulty wiring in the aft fuselage, as shown in Figure 1. The use of carbon fibre reinforced polymer laminates is becoming more prevalent in large passenger, cargo and military aircraft structures such as the fuselage, wings, empennage and engines, making it necessary to understand their fire structural resistance. A concern with using polymer matrix composites in aircraft structures is their high flammability and poor fire resistance. Polymer matrix composites, including carbon-epoxy laminates, are a potential fire hazard due to the heat, smoke and toxic fumes released when they burn [6]. There is also concern for the structural integrity as thermal softening and pyrolysis of the epoxy matrix and weakening of the carbon fibre reinforcement can cause the material to distort and fail [6].

There has been a large amount of research into the structural performance of laminates in fire [7-33]. Much of this research has focused on glass fibre reinforced laminates under compressive or tensile loading; however carbon-fibre laminates are used more extensively in aircraft and therefore their fire structural performance needs to be investigated. Carbon-fibre laminates behave differently to fiberglass composites when exposed to fire as the carbon fibres can oxidize at high temperature. Although there have been a number of studies examining the fire properties of carbon-fibre laminates, most have concentrated on the fire reaction properties (e.g. heat release rate) and the fire structural response under compressive loading [29-35].

Most carbon-epoxy laminates used in aircraft structures have quasi-isotropic or near quasi-isotropic ply stacking sequences, although arrangement of the 0° , $+45^\circ$, -45° and 90° plies is a design variable dependent on several factors. For example, laminate structures subjected to bending loads often have 0° plies at the surfaces whereas laminates carrying shear-dominated stresses or at risk of impact may have 45° surface plies. The ply stacking sequence also depends on the thickness; thin laminates are often stacked with the fibre direction changing per ply layer (e.g. $[0/+45/-45/90]$) whereas thick laminates may be stacked in multiple layers of the same ply orientation (e.g. $[0_n/+45_n/-45_n/90_n]$, where n is usually 2, 3 or 4). While the fire structural performance of carbon-epoxy laminates representative of the materials used in aircraft structures have been studied [33, 34], the studies have been confined to a single ply stacking sequence. No studies have attempted to determine whether the fire structural behavior of quasi-isotropic carbon-epoxy laminates is dependent on the ply stacking sequence.

This paper presents an experimental study into the influence of the ply stacking sequence of an aircraft structural-grade carbon-epoxy laminate on the fire structural performance. The tensile structural responses of laminates having 0° or 45° surface plies are compared when exposed to one-sided radiant heating representative of fire. The influence of the ply stacking sequence on the thermal response, deformation, and tensile structural survivability leading to failure of carbon-epoxy laminates is determined, and related to fire-induced damage. A practical objective of this work is to provide the aerospace industry with a better understanding of the fire structural performance of carbon-epoxy laminates and how the ply stacking sequence can be tailored to increase fire structural survivability under tensile loads.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

2.1 Manufacture

The laminates were made using unidirectional Hexcel AS4/3501-6 carbon-fibre epoxy prepreg. Quasi-isotropic laminates were made with 0° or $+45^\circ$ surface plies, which are respectively designated *Laminates 1* and *2* in Table 1. Both of these laminates contained a total of 48 plies (6.6 mm thick) in which the fibre angle changed by 45° per ply. Laminates with three 0° plies located at the surfaces or mid-plane were also made, and these are designated *Laminates 3* and *4*, respectively. These two laminates also contained a total of 48 plies (6.6 mm thick).

During ply stacking the laminates were de-bulked after every four plies for three minutes to ensure air was removed from between the plies. The laminates were vacuum bagged and cured in an

autoclave at 120°C and 90 psi for 60 mins. The cured laminates have a fibre volume fraction of 65% and a glass transition temperature of 210°C.

Name	Sequence	Tensile Failure Stress
Laminate 1	[0/+45/90/-45/0/+45/90/-45/0/+45/90/-45]s	588 ± 10 MPa
Laminate 2	[+45/90/-45/0/+45/90/-45/0/+45/90/-45/0]s	555 ± 30 MPa
Laminate 3	[0/0/0/+45/90/-45/+45/90/-45/+45/90/-45]s	540 ± 55 MPa
Laminate 4	[+45/90/-45/+45/90/-45/+45/90/-45/0/0/0]s	530 ± 20 MPa

Table 1 Laminate ply sequence and tensile failure stress at 20°C.

2.2 Fire Structural Testing Methodology

Fire structural testing involved loading the laminate sample in tension to a fixed load level while simultaneously heating one side using a radiant heater (as shown schematically in Figure 2). The laminate samples were 600 mm long and 50 mm wide, and were loaded in the 0° fibre direction using a 250 kN MTS machine fitted with a smoke extraction system. The applied constant loads ranged from 10% to 80% of the tensile failure stress at 20°C, which are given for the different laminates in Table 1. When under constant load, the laminate was exposed to an incident radiant heat flux of 50kW/m². This flux heated the front surface to a maximum temperature of ~700°C. The heat flux was generated by a conical electric resistive heater (diameter 200 mm) taken from a cone calorimeter. The laminate and heater were in a vertical orientation with the heater placed 25 mm from the sample surface. Only a 100 mm long section of the laminate was exposed directly to the heat flux; the other surfaces of the sample were thermally insulated using Fiberfrax® 550 K ceramic fibre wool. The front and back face temperatures of the laminate samples were monitored continuously during testing using K-type thermocouples. In addition, the internal temperature of the laminates was measured using embedded thermocouple located between the two middle plies.

Figure 2 Fire under load testing set up.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Temperature Profiles of Carbon-Fibre Epoxy Laminates

Figure 3 shows the measured temperature rise at the front and back surfaces as well as the middle of the laminates with increasing heat flux exposure time. Multiple tests were performed and the temperatures were highly consistent between tests performed on the same laminate. The front surface was rapidly heated within the initial few minutes and then reached a quasi-steady state temperature of

~700°C. The temperature measurements reveal that the heating rate and maximum temperature of the front surface was not affected significantly by the ply stacking sequence (Fig 3a). However, the internal and back surface temperatures were dependent on the ply orientation. The temperatures at the middle of the laminates were lower (up to ~80°C) when a 0° ply was placed at the surface (Fig 3b).

Figure 3 Temperature rise of the laminate with increasing time at a heat flux of 50kW/m² at a) front surface b) middle c) back surface.

However, the back surface temperatures of the laminates with 0° surface plies were hotter (up to ~80°C) than the composites with 45° surface plies after several minutes (Fig 3c). These differences are due to differences in the length and crack opening of delaminations in laminates with a 0° or 45° surface ply. The mechanisms controlling the initiation and growth of fire-induced delaminations are

complex, and may be due to a mismatch in thermal strains between plies aligned in different orientations, differences in thermal strains due to the steep temperature gradient through the composite, and internal pressures from volatile gases generated as a by-product of the decomposition reaction process of the polymer matrix. Figure 4 shows the four types of quasi-isotropic laminate following exposure to the heat flux. The width and number of long delamination cracks was greater in the laminates with the 45° surface ply. The laminates with the 0° surface ply also contained delaminations, although many of these were narrower and shorter. Also, the laminates with a 45° surface ply had a long and widest delamination along the mid-plane, which was absent in the 0° surface ply composites. Delaminations create air gaps within a laminate which reduce the effective through-thickness thermal conductivity. The temperature difference through-the-thickness of the different laminates may be due to these delaminations between the plies. The large mid-plane delamination in the laminates with a 45° surface ply will trap heat ahead of the crack and reduce heat flow behind the crack, resulting in the higher and lower back surface temperatures than the 0° surface ply composites, as shown in Figs 3b and 3c.

Figure 4 Delamination cracks after exposure to the heat flux of 50kW/m² from the left side in a) Laminate 1 b) Laminate 2 c) Laminate 3 d) Laminate 4.

Delamination cracking is facilitated by fibre orientation variations between neighbouring plies as each ply orientation has a different coefficient of thermal expansion, as shown in Figure 5. These thermal expansions result in thermal strains between different neighbouring ply orientations and cause delamination cracking.

Figure 2 CTE's in the 0° and 90° directions of a carbon epoxy laminate. [36]

3.3 Tensile Fire Structural Testing of Carbon-Fibre Epoxy Laminates

The axial extension of the laminates was monitored with increasing exposure time to the heat flux until they failed. Figure 6 compares extension-time curves measured for the laminates with a 0° or 45° surface ply at different applied tensile stress levels. Axial extension is not dependent significantly on the ply orientation as the laminates showed similar increases in extension rate with increasing applied stress due to the combined effects of thermal expansion, thermal softening, matrix decomposition and progressive ply failure. The axial thermal expansion coefficient of the laminates is low and therefore most of the extension is caused by softening, decomposition and ply failure. The laminates experienced progressive softening and decomposition as they became hotter with increasing exposure time to the heat flux, and this caused them to elongate until they failure. As mentioned, softening of the epoxy matrix occurred at the temperatures of about 210°C (T_g). Feih et al. [31] measured a reduction in the tensile strength of carbon fibres above $\sim 400^\circ\text{C}$ due to the growth of surface flaws. The fibre modulus also decreases when heated above $\sim 500^\circ\text{C}$ in air due to oxidation-induced fibre thinning, however other than the fibres at the surface ply oxidation cannot occur because the out-gassing of decomposition volatiles restrict access of air into the laminate. For this reason, the fibre modulus within the sub-surface plies does not change, although there is significant fibre weakening when the plies are heated above $\sim 400^\circ\text{C}$. Therefore, most of the axial extension of the laminates during fire structural testing is due to matrix softening, decomposition and ply failure.

Figure 6 Axial displacements of the laminates with increasing heat flux exposure time. The percentage values define the applied tensile stress as a percentage of the ultimate strength at room temperature.

Figure 7 shows the effect of applied tension stress on the failure time of the carbon-epoxy laminates when exposed to the heat flux. Failure always occurred by tensile rupture of the plies. The failure times were not significantly influenced by the ply orientation when the applied tensile stress was high (above $\sim 50\%$ of the ultimate strength or ~ 300 MPa). The failure times at high stresses were short (less than 100–200 seconds), and therefore only the region immediately below the heat surface was sufficiently hot to soften the epoxy matrix and weaken the carbon fibres. Most of the stress is carried by the 0° plies to the laminate, with the other ply orientations making a much smaller contribution to the strength. At high stress when the 0° ply nearest the heated surface quickly fails, and this causes the remaining load-bearing plies to be instantaneously over-loaded thereby complete failure within a short heating time. A large difference in the softening rate and failure time occurred between the laminates with 0° or 45° surface plies when the applied stress was reduced below ~ 300 MPa. This difference was more pronounced when multiple 0° plies were placed at the heated surface (Laminate 3), which failed up to 1500 seconds sooner than Laminate 4. By placing the 0° plies below the surface, which is the case for Laminates 2 and 4, there is a thermal lag due to the low thermal conductivity of the laminate. This slows the softening rate of the sub-surface 0° plies which thereby increases the fire survivability of the laminates with a 45° surface ply.

Figure 3 Failure times of the carbon-epoxy laminates exposed to the heat flux of 50kW/m².

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study has proven that the fire structural resistance of quasi-isotropic carbon-epoxy laminates used in aircraft structures is dependent on the ply stacking sequence. The internal temperature of the laminates was dependent on their ply orientation. Laminates with a 45° surface ply (0° middle ply) reached higher internal temperatures close to the heated surface than laminates with a 0° surface ply (45° middle ply). This occurs because 45° surface ply laminates experience larger and wider delamination cracking which traps heat near from front surface. A further consequence of this is laminates with a 45° surface ply have lower back face temperature. Laminates with a 45° surface ply experience more extensive heat-induced delamination cracking which lowers the effective through-thickness thermal conductivity. It is also found that the softening rate and failure time depends on the ply orientation at low applied tensile stresses (less than ~50% of the ultimate strength); with a 45° surface ply providing superior fire structural resistance. The insulating effect of the wider and larger delamination cracks in the 45° surface ply laminates slowed the thermal softening rate of the load-bearing (0°) plies located towards the back surface, and this extended the fire structural survivability under tensile loading. The dependence of the fire structural performance on the ply stacking pattern is related to differences in heat conduction, heat-induced delamination cracking, and other softening mechanisms between the laminates, and should be a consideration in the fire safe design of aircraft composite structures.

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